

<부록> 분석 대상 문헌

- [1] Amador, J. M., Glassmeyer, D., & Brakonieccki, A. (2025). Teachers' noticing of proportional reasoning. *Journal of Mathematics Teacher Education*, 28(4), 879-907. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10857-024-09625-7>
- [2] Amador, J. M., Weston, T. L., & Kosko, K. (2025). Video prompts as scaffolding for noticing students' mathematical thinking using 360-degree videos: Comparing what is noticed with how. *Journal für Mathematik-Didaktik*, 46(1), 4. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13138-024-00255-3>
- [3] Beilstein, S. O., Perry, M., & Bates, M. S. (2017). Prompting meaningful analysis from pre-service teachers using elementary mathematics video vignettes. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 63, 285-295. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.01.005>
- [4] Brunvand, S., & Fishman, B. (2006). Investigating the impact of the availability of scaffolds on preservice teacher noticing and learning from video. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 35(2), 151-174. <https://doi.org/10.2190/L353-X356-72W7-42L9>
- [5] Ergene, B. C., & Bostan, M. I. (2025). Nurturing pre-service teachers' professional noticing skills through pedagogies of practice. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 23(5), 1309-1339. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-024-10519-6>
- [6] Farrell, M., Martin, M., Böheim, R., Renkl, A., Rieß, W., Könings, K. D., & Seidel, T. (2024). Signaling cues and focused prompts for professional vision support: The interplay of instructional design and situational interest in preservice teachers' video analysis. *Instructional Science*, 52(6), 879-917. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11251-024-09662-y>
- [7] Gabel, S., Keskin, Ö., & Gegenfurtner, A. (2025). Comparing the effects of a specific task instruction and prompts on pre-service teachers' noticing of classroom management situations. *Zeitschrift für Erziehungswissenschaft*, 28(1), 105-123. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11618-024-01276-x>
- [8] Gabel, S., Keskin, Ö., Kollar, I., Lewalter, D., & Gegenfurtner, A. (2023). Guiding pre-service teachers' visual attention through instructional settings: An eye-tracking study. *Frontiers in Education*, 8, 1282848. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2023.1282848>
- [9] Irmer, M., Traub, D., & Neuhaus, B. J. (2024). Fostering ePCK in pre-service biology teacher education using adaptive scaffolding in a video-based simulation. *Cogent Education*, 11(1), 2422272. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2024.2422272>
- [10] Killian, J. N., & Liu, J. (2018). Effect of focused observation on preservice music teachers' mention of students. *Bulletin of the Council for Research in Music Education*, 216, 31-46. <https://doi.org/10.5406/bulcouresmusedu.216.0031>
- [11] Killian, J. N., Henninger, J. C., & Williams, B. A. (2023). It's about time: An examination of the importance of timing on positivity of preservice music educators' teaching reflections. *International Journal of Music Education*, 41(1), 97-110. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02557614221090582>
- [12] Martin, M., Farrell, M., Seidel, T., Rieß, W., Könings, K. D., van Merriënboer, J. J.,

- & Renkl, A. (2022). Focused self-explanation prompts and segmenting foster pre-service teachers' professional vision—but only during training! *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 19(1), 34. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-022-00331-z>
- [13] Michalsky, T. (2020). Preservice teachers' professional vision for and capacity to teach self-regulated learning: Effects of scaffolding level. *Teachers College Record*, 122(3), 1-48. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016146812012200310>
- [14] Nickl, M., Sommerhoff, D., Böheim, R., Ufer, S., & Seidel, T. (2023). Fostering pre-service teachers' assessment skills in a video simulation. *Zeitschrift für Pädagogische Psychologie*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1024/1010-0652/a000362>
- [15] Nickl, M., Sommerhoff, D., Radkowitzsch, A., Huber, S. A., Bauer, E., Ufer, S., & Seidel, T. (2024). Effects of real-time adaptivity of scaffolding: Supporting pre-service mathematics teachers' assessment skills in simulations. *Learning and Instruction*, 94, 101994. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2024.101994>
- [16] Nilsson, P., & Karlsson, G. (2019). Capturing student teachers' pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) using CoRes and digital technology. *International Journal of Science Education*, 41(4), 419-447. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2018.1551642>
- [17] Roth McDuffie, A., Foote, M. Q., Bolson, C., Turner, E. E., Aguirre, J. M., Bartell, T. G., & Land, T. (2014). Using video analysis to support prospective K-8 teachers' noticing of students' multiple mathematical knowledge bases. *Journal of Mathematics Teacher Education*, 17(3), 245-270. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10857-013-9257-0>
- [18] Santagata, R. (2009). Designing video-based professional development for mathematics teachers in low-performing schools. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 60(1), 38-51. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487108328485>
- [19] Sommerhoff, D., Codreanu, E., Nickl, M., Ufer, S., & Seidel, T. (2023). Pre-service teachers' learning of diagnostic skills in a video-based simulation: Effects of conceptual vs. interconnecting prompts on judgment accuracy and the diagnostic process. *Learning and Instruction*, 83, 101689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2022.101689>
- [20] Telgmann, L., & Müller, K. (2023). Training and prompting pre-service teachers' noticing in a standardized classroom simulation: A mobile eye-tracking study. *Frontiers in Education*, 8, 1266800. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1266800>
- [21] Weston, T. L., & Amador, J. M. (2021). Investigating student teachers' noticing using 360 video of their own teaching. *Journal of Technology and Teacher Education*, 29(3), 309-338. <https://doi.org/10.70725/532779nssvre>
- [22] Wilkes, T., Stark, L., Trempler, K., & Stark, R. (2022). Contrastive video examples in teacher education: A matter of sequence and prompts. *Frontiers in Education*, 7, 869664. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2022.869664>